

*33rd Electric Vehicle Symposium (EVS33)
Portland, Oregon, June 14 - 17, 2020*

**Exploring the dynamic influences between the conventional,
electric and hybrid powertrains on a global market scale**

Amir Mirzadeh Phirouzabadi, David Savage, Karen Blackmore, James Juniper

The University of Newcastle, 409 Hunter Street, Newcastle NSW 2300 Australia, amir.mirzadeh@uon.edu.au

Summary

Understanding the scale and direction of emerging and incumbent vehicle powertrains is critical for accelerating the transition to the green mobility economy. Our aim is to explore the dynamic influences between the conventional, electric and hybrid vehicle powertrains on a global market scale. Based on the Technological Innovation System framework and the Lotka-Volterra model, we argue that a powertrain with positive or negative market growth can both support and inhibit the market growth of the other powertrains. Using Google traffic search data (2004-2016), our results show that their relationships are not always competitive, but symbiotic, parasitic and amensalism.

1 Introduction and background

Understanding and analysing the scale and direction of the powertrains of internal combustion engine vehicles (ICEV), battery electric vehicles (BEV) and hybrid electric vehicles (HEV) in the era of ferment is critical for accelerating the transition to the green mobility economy [1]. The era of ferment for the case of emerging sustainable innovations such as electrified mobility is characterized by technological discontinuity, large investments, increased technological experimentations, high risks and uncertainty and the frequent entries and exits firms, and late returns on investment [2]. It is, hence, critical to draw insights from the complicated dynamic relationship between the emerging and incumbent powertrain technologies in order to direct their pathways and accelerate the speed of socio-technical transitions towards more sustainable options.

Some qualitative and quantitative studies have investigated the interactions between the powertrain technologies in terms of technical performances such as knowledge development [1, 3-5]. For instance, using joint and non-joint patents data, it was found that ICEV, HEV and BEV have established relationships other than competition and symbiosis between one another, such as parasitism and commensalism [4, 5]. However, not only technical indicators such as patents and bibliometric data but also economic indicators such as West Texas Intermediate (WTI) price, GDP growth and R&D investments are unable to forecast the vehicle demands of BEV and HEV [6]. This is because new technologies such as BEV and HEV are still in the early stages of their technological life cycle and have recently gained a market momentum. Therefore, there are not sufficient information to capture and measure their market performance to draw sophisticated insights and implications for demand forecasting and policy issues.

Some theories such as schemas and scripts [7], social construction of technology (SCOT) [8, 9], Discourse theory [10] and sociology of expectations theory [11-14] and the Technological Innovation System (TIS) framework [15-17] point out that narratives, rhetorical visions, promises and expectations shaped around the future performance of emerging technologies are critical for their market development. In accordance with the Technological Innovation System (TIS) framework, one of the main dynamics for the development,

diffusion and utilisation of an emerging technology is ‘guidance of the search’, which is the process of collective visions, promises, beliefs, and expectations that not only direct the development path of a powertrain technology but also refer to the real time representation of its market future in society [2, 11, 14]. The collective visions, promises, beliefs, and expectations shaped around BEV in the late 80s led to intensive R&D investment such as the introduction of the EV1 model by GM and supporting laws and regulation such as the enactment of the Zero Emission Vehicles (ZEV) mandate in California [18]. Therefore, the socio-technical performance indicators such as ‘guidance of the search’ outweigh the technical or economic performance indicators such as bibliometrics, patents, and R&D investments in the early stages of development [2, 11, 14].

Using the TIS framework and the biological ecology relationships, [Mirzadeh Phirouzabadi, et al. \[2\]](#) argue that two technologies may influence and interact with one another through their mutual dynamics. They argue that the guidance of the search dynamic in a powertrain technology can become coupled with the guidance of the search in another technology as the collective visions, promises, beliefs, and expectations shaped around the former powertrain can cross over the boundary of the system and be influenced by the collective visions, promises, beliefs, and expectations shaped around the latter powertrain. They called the interacting coupled guidance of search dynamics as ‘guidance of search co-dynamic’. Other studies have implied to the influences between technologies in terms of expectations and beliefs, “Expectations concerning a specific technology are of course influenced by expectations concerning competing (existing and new) technologies. Rosenberg [14] for example states that “Expectations of continued improvement in a new technology may therefore lead to postponement of an innovation, to a slowing down in the rate of its diffusion or to an adoption in a modified form to permit greater future flexibility”. High expectations regarding a new technology may for example lead to an increase in R&D and marketing efforts for the existing technology and cause a sailing ship effect.” [14, p450]. For instance, [Alkemade and Suurs \[14\]](#) found out that the three emerging technologies of biofuels, hydrogen and natural gas have been competing with one another in terms of shaping visions, promises and expectations about the market future in Netherlands.

Our aim hence is to explore the dynamical influences between ICEV, HEV, and BEV on a global market scale, and not in terms of merely technical performance indicators such as bibliometric or patents data, but in terms of a socio-technical performance indicator that can illustrate the guidance of the search or direction for powertrain technologies. Based on the TIS framework, we conceptualise that the powertrain technologies are influenced and interacting with one another in terms of shaping the guidance of the search. The impact between the powertrain technologies may not necessary be pure competitive. [Mirzadeh Phirouzabadi, et al. \[2\]](#) argue that the interactions between two technologies can go beyond purely competition or purely cooperation. Roadmaps can be used to explain why technologies interact and influence each other beyond competition. Technologies that neatly fit into existing roadmaps, can utilize the already existing policies, action plans, expectations and promises originally expressed for different technologies [15-17]. This can be observed in fields such as sustainability transition where the government’s visions and public policies simultaneously support various renewable energy technologies [19]. Taken the six of biological relationship mode, [Mirzadeh Phirouzabadi, et al. \[2\]](#) argue that technologies may influence one another in the form of competition, symbiosis, parasitism, commensalism, amensalism, and neutralism.

- Competition: when the directed expectations, beliefs, visions around one powertrain technology is negatively affected by the directed expectations, beliefs, visions around powertrain technology and vice versa,
- Symbiosis: when the directed expectations, beliefs, visions around one powertrain technology is positively affected by the directed expectations, beliefs, visions around another powertrain technology and vice versa,
- Parasitism: when the directed expectations, beliefs, visions around one powertrain technology is positively affected by the directed expectations, beliefs, visions around another powertrain technology, while the directed expectations, beliefs, visions around the latter powertrain technology is negatively affected by the directed expectations, beliefs, visions around the former powertrain technology,
- Commensalism: when the relationship is one sided and the directed expectations, beliefs, visions around one powertrain technology is positively affected by the directed expectations, beliefs, visions around another powertrain technology;

- Amensalism: when the relationship is one sided and the directed expectations, beliefs, visions around one powertrain technology is negatively affected by the directed expectations, beliefs, visions around another powertrain technology, and
- Neutralism: when there's no effects between the two powertrain systems whatsoever.

We apply the biological Lotka-Volterra (L-V) equations model which can determine as well as quantify the relationships between the powertrain technologies [20, 21]. The L-V model can build the classic S-shaped curve of a powertrain system by formulating not only its positive and negative endogenous feedback, but also the positive and negative exogenous feedback trading with other powertrain systems. Several studies have demonstrated that the L-V equations have simulated the real world data with a better performance compared with models such as Logistic models, Gompertz model, Sharif-Kabir model [22-25], simple exponential function [22], and Bass model [24-26]. The L-V model has been applied to not only the interactions among various technologies such as skyscraper and cement technologies [22], new renewable energies and biomedicines [27], information and communications technologies [28], and powertrain systems [4, 5], but also has been interpreted for various areas such as market formation [23, 29, 30], resource mobilizations [31-34], and institutional design and change [35], and knowledge development using patents data [4, 5].

This article is structured as follows. Section 2 the methodology. Section 3 presents results, and Section 4 presents our discussion and conclusions.

2 Methodology

2.1 The Google search traffic (GOST)

The guidance of the search for a powertrain technology is measured by extracting the Google traffic search data (GOST). The GOST data can better generate insights on the development, diffusion and utilisation of the new emerging powertrain technologies of BEV and HEV in the early stage. Because the data give a direct and collective indication of the various players' behaviour within the powertrain system such as academics, entrepreneurs, technology developers, suppliers, consumers and customer, NGOs, and governments. For examples, customers and consumers are directing the search for BEV and HEV by searching through new model brands on Google such as the Toyota Prius, the Tesla Model S, and the Nissan Leaf. Additionally, they can cover some of the purchase decision making process stages: 1) problem awareness, 2) information search, 3) evaluation of alternatives, 4) decision to purchase, and 5) actions following purchase [6]. Governmental actors direct the search for these powertrains by setting up roadmaps and policy action plans, incentives and regulation, and standards such as the ZEV mandate, which are being searched by the manufactures. And academics guide the search over Google (for example Google Patent or Google Scholar) by entering keywords related to the researches on the various scientific and technological aspects of the powertrain technologies. One of the main advantages of the GOST data is that Google normalises all the results of the search statistics and divide them by a common variable to eliminate the influence of external forces [6].

2.2 Data collection

The GOST data are extracted from Google Trend and are analysed for the period of 2004-2016. The start year 2004 was chosen as the Google data was available only since then. Based on some recent studies [4, 5, 36, 37], we divided the period into two individual episodes of 2004-2007 (toward hybridisation) and 2008-2016 (toward mass commercialisation), and analysed the data accordingly.

Figure 1 demonstrates the GOST data of the three powertrain technologies over the two episodes of toward hybridisation and toward mass commercialisation as well as the entire time frame (2004-2016). It is clear that the emerging BEV powertrain technology constantly differentiate itself from the other two powertrain technologies. The HEV powertrain though differentiates itself from the incumbent ICEV in the first episode, its distinct position fades away in the second episode.

Figure 1: The GOST data for ICEV, HEV, and BEV (2004-2016)

2.3 The L-V equations

The L-V equations model can express the intra-population and inter-population interactions between the three powertrain technologies of ICEV, HEV, and BEV in the form of three differential equations as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d(GOST_{ICEV,t})}{dt} &= (a_{ICEV} - b_{ICEV}(GOST_{ICEV,t}) - c_{ICEV,HEV}(GOST_{HEV,t}) \\ &\quad - c_{ICEV,BEV}(GOST_{BEV,t}))(GOST_{ICEV,t}) \\ &= a_{ICEV}(GOST_{ICEV,t}) - b_{ICEV}(GOST_{ICEV,t})^2 \\ &\quad - c_{ICEV,HEV}(GOST_{HEV,t})(GOST_{ICEV,t}) \\ &\quad - c_{ICEV,BEV}(GOST_{BEV,t})(GOST_{ICEV,t}) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d(GOST_{HEV,t})}{dt} &= (a_{HEV} - b_{HEV}(GOST_{HEV,t}) - c_{HEV,ICEV}(GOST_{ICEV,t}) \\ &\quad - c_{HEV,BEV}(GOST_{BEV,t}))(GOST_{HEV,t}) \\ &= a_{HEV}(GOST_{HEV,t}) - b_{HEV}(GOST_{HEV,t})^2 \\ &\quad - c_{HEV,ICEV}(GOST_{ICEV,t})(GOST_{HEV,t}) \\ &\quad - c_{HEV,BEV}(GOST_{BEV,t})(GOST_{HEV,t}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d(GOST_{BEV,t})}{dt} &= (a_{BEV} - b_{BEV}(GOST_{BEV,t}) - c_{BEV,ICEV}(GOST_{ICEV,t}) \\ &\quad - c_{BEV,HEV}(GOST_{HEV,t}))(GOST_{BEV,t}) \\ &= a_{BEV}(GOST_{BEV,t}) - b_{BEV}(GOST_{BEV,t})^2 \\ &\quad - c_{BEV,ICEV}(GOST_{ICEV,t})(GOST_{BEV,t}) \\ &\quad - c_{BEV,HEV}(GOST_{HEV,t})(GOST_{BEV,t}) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

a_{ICEV} and b_{ICEV} are the intrinsic growth and decline rates of ICEV when it is living alone. When a_{ICEV} is divided by b_{ICEV} , i.e. $a_{ICEV}/|b_{ICEV}|$, we can calculate the carrying capacity (k) of ICEV, which is the maximum capacity related to saturation value of ICEV imposed by limited resources [38]. $C_{ICEV,BEV}$ as the external interaction parameter is the growth effect of BEV on ICEV when both are living with one another. Depending the effect is positive, negative, or neutral, one of the six modes of interactions can be established between ICEV and BEV.

Since our GOST data is discrete, we applied the discrete time formats of the L-V equations [39]. For the case of ICEV technology, they are as follows:

$$GOST_{ICEV,t+1} = \frac{\alpha_{ICEV}(GOST_{ICEV,t})}{1 + \beta_{ICEV}(GOST_{ICEV,t}) + \gamma_{ICEV,HEV}(GOST_{HEV,t}) + \gamma_{ICEV,BEV}(GOST_{BEV,t})} \quad (4)$$

Here, α_i corresponds to a_i , β_i to b_i , and γ_{ij} to c_{ij} . They can be calculated through one another as follows [39]:

$$\alpha_{ICEV} = \ln \alpha_{ICEV} \quad (5)$$

$$\beta_{ICEV} = \frac{\beta_{ICEV} \ln \alpha_{ICEV}}{\alpha_{ICEV} - 1} \quad (6)$$

$$\gamma_{ICEV,HEV} = \frac{\gamma_{ICEV,HEV} \ln \alpha_{ICEV}}{\alpha_{ICEV} - 1} \quad (7)$$

2.4 Method

We have utilised both SPSS and Microsoft Excel in order to estimate and calculate the parameters using the non-linear least-square method and the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm. The initial value of α_i , β_i and γ_{ij} was set to 1, 0.001, and 0.001, respectively [23, 30, 40].

3 Results

The estimation results for the first episode ‘toward hybridisation’ (2004-2007) as shown in Table 2 indicate that ICEV is found as the most searched powertrain technology in the search queries of Google Search with the intrinsic search popularity growth rate of 5.94E-01. BEV is found as the least searched powertrain technology, possessing a bit lower intrinsic search popularity growth rate than HEV ($a=3.00E-01$ and $a=3.38E-01$, respectively). We found that BEV possesses the highest carrying capacity for receiving search queries in Google Search, followed by ICEV and HEV ($k=1.06E+02$, $k=1.11E+01$, and $k=8.50E+00$, respectively). The estimated external interaction parameters in Table 3 indicate that HEV and BEV are competing with one another for getting popularity via the search queries in Google Search ($C=6.90E-02$ and $C=3.26E-03$). BEV also acts as predator to the search popularity growth of ICEV via a parasitic relationship mode ($C=7.89E-03$ and $C=-4.93E-02$), while HEV enjoys the search popularity growth of the latter powertrain technology via a commensal relationship ($C=0$ and $C=-3.25E-02$).

In the second episode ‘toward mass commercialisation’ (2008-2016), we found HEV as the most searched powertrain technology in the search queries of Google Search with the intrinsic search popularity growth rate of 3.97E-01, followed by BEV ($a=3.38E-01$) and ICEV ($a=3.25E-01$). BEV, however, remains as the powertrain technology with the largest carrying capacity for receiving search queries in Google Search ($k=1.38E+01$), followed by HEV ($k=6.51E+00$) and ICEV ($k=5.86E+00$). The interaction results in Table 3 indicate that BEV and HEV establish no meaningful, significant relationship with each other in the second episode. While on the one hand, ICEV acts as prey in a parasitic relationship with BEV ($C=6.45E-03$ and $C=-6.46E-02$), on the other hand, the incumbent powertrain acts as predator in a parasitic relationship with HEV ($C=2.56E-02$ and $C=-2.24E-02$).

Table 2: The parameter estimation results for Google trend

	Parameters						R ²
	a_i	b_i	$k_i=a_i/ b_i $	$C_{i,ICEV}$	$C_{i,HEV}$	$C_{i,BEV}$	
‘Toward hybridisation’ (2004–2007)							
ICEV	5.94E-01 (4.14E+00***)	5.37E-02 (1.96E+00*)	1.11E+01	- -	-6.94E-03 (-9.22E-01)	7.89E-03 (1.67E+00*)	0.507
HEV	3.38E-01 (3.18E+00***)	3.97E-02 (2.13E+00**)	8.50E+00	-3.25E-02 (- 2.21E+00**)	- -	3.26E-03 (5.65E-01***)	0.618
BEV	3.00E-01 (2.37E+00**)	-2.83E-03 (-5.79E-01)	1.06E+02	-4.93E-02 (- 2.84E+00***)	6.90E-02 (1.73E+00*)	- -	0.622
‘Toward mass commercialisation’ (2008–2016)							
ICEV	3.25E-01 (1.12E+01***)	5.54E-02 (2.97E+00***)	5.86E+00	- -	-2.24E-02 (- 2.92E+00**)	6.45E-03 (2.44E+00***)	0.722
HEV	3.97E-01 (7.44E+00***)	-6.10E-02 (- 4.40E+00***)	6.51E+00	2.56E-02 (5.26E+00***)	- -	3.00E-02 (1.19E+00)	0.922
BEV	3.38E-01 (1.02E+01***)	2.45E-02 (7.00E+00***)	1.38E+01	-6.46E-02 (- 6.08E+00***)	2.57E-02 (1.39E+00)	- -	0.910
The entire period (1985–2016)							
ICEV	2.08E-01 (1.67E+01***)	2.93E-02 (3.61E+00***)	7.08E+00	- -	-1.03E-02 (- 2.80E+00***)	3.84E-03 (2.61E+00***)	0.821
HEV	2.50E-02 (1.08E+01***)	1.18E-02 (2.29E+00**)	2.12E+00	-1.98E-02 (- 1.96E+00**)	- -	1.17E-03 (6.02E-01)	0.736
BEV	2.11E-01 (1.03E+01***)	8.66E-03 (3.70E+00***)	2.44E+01	-2.23E-02 (- 3.11E+00***)	2.60E-02 (1.57E+00*)	- -	0.734

Notes: *, **, *** significant at $p < 0.1$; $p < 0.05$; $p < 0.01$

As indicated by the overall estimation results in Table 2, BEV is found as the most searched powertrain technology in the search queries of Google Search with the intrinsic search popularity growth rate of 2.11E-01 over the entire period of 2004-2016, closely followed by ICEV (2.08E-01), but by far followed by HEV (2.50E-02). The emerging powertrain is also found to possess the largest carrying capacity for receiving search queries in Google Search ($k=2.44E+01$), followed by ICEV ($k=7.08E+00$) and HEV ($k=2.12E+00$) over the entire period. The overall external interaction parameters estimated in Table 3 indicate that BEV is inhibiting the search popularity growth of HEV in Google Search vis-à-vis an amensalism relationship ($C=0$ and $C=2.60E-02$). The overall BEV-ICEV relationship mode and nature resemble the individual episodes as BEV overall benefits from the search popularity growth of ICEV while inhibits its growth in the parasitic relationship ($C=3.84E-03$ and $C=-2.23E-02$). Finally, I found HEV and ICEV benefitting from the search popularity growth of one another through a mutually symbiotic relationship ($C=-1.98E-02$ and $C=-1.03E-02$).

Table 3: Dynamic interactions between powertrain technologies in terms of Google trend

Technologies		‘Toward hybridisation’ (2004–2007)		‘Toward mass commercialisation’ (2008–2016)		The entire period (2004–2016)	
i	j	$C_{i,j}$	$C_{j,i}$	$C_{i,j}$	$C_{j,i}$	$C_{i,j}$	$C_{j,i}$
BEV	HEV	6.90E-02	3.26E-03	0	0	2.60E-02	0
		Competition		neutralism		amensalism	
ICEV	BEV	7.89E-03	-4.93E-02	6.45E-03	-6.46E-02	3.84E-03	-2.23E-02
		prey-predator		prey-predator		prey-predator	
HEV	ICEV	-3.25E-02	0	2.56E-02	-2.24E-02	-1.98E-02	-1.03E-02
		commensalism		prey-predator		Symbiosis	

4 Discussion and conclusions

While the majority of the transportation studies associated the socio-technical development of powertrain technologies to factors such as oil price [41], suppliers’ capabilities [42], infrastructure [43], carmakers’ strategies [44], increasing returns [18], and legitimisation [18], some recent studies have started to demonstrate that the performance of a powertrain technology influence the performance of another powertrain technology [4, 5]. While these recent studies investigated the influences between powertrain technologies in terms of technical performance such as knowledge development using patents data, the results of our paper showed that the powertrain technologies influence and interact with one another even in terms of socio-technical performances, i.e. guidance of the search using Google search traffic data. A powertrain technology with a positive or negative intrinsic search popularity growth may create either positive or negative search popularity externalities, or both, in other powertrain technologies. The technology management literature recognises these positive or negative externalities as the ‘mirror effects’ of the positive or negative intrinsic growth [45, 46]. It is argued by [Mirzadeh Phirouzabadi, et al. \[2\]](#) that the ‘guidance of the search co-dynamics’ shaped by the ‘coupled guidance of the search dynamics’ between the powertrain technologies carry the positive and negative externalities. So, the positive or negative expectations, beliefs or visions shaped around one technology can spilled over into other surrounding technologies through guidance of the search co-dynamics.

We observed that the intrinsic search popularity and carrying capacity of the powertrain technologies changed from the first to the second episode. While we found ICEV as the most popular powertrain in the search queries of Google in the first episode, it became the least popular powertrain in the second episode. On the contrary, BEV that was found as the least popular powertrain in the search queries of Google in the first episode, it became much more popular in the second episode. This can be linked to the guidance of search dynamics that usually follow a typical pattern with alternating cycles of hype and disappointment over time [11, 14]. A hype cycle for a powertrain technology occurs when it experiences sudden positive expectations followed by a sharp decline in its positive expectations or a rise in negative expectations. A disappointment cycle for a powertrain technology occurs when the initial high promises and expectations shaped around the technology have not been met at all.

Additionally, we observed temporal shiftings in the nature, as well as the extent and mode of interaction between the powertrain technologies. The competitive relationship between BEV and HEV in the first episode entirely changed in the second episode as we found no meaningful relationship between them anymore. Or after HEV started to benefit from the commensal relationship with ICEV in the first episode, its growth ended up being inhibited by ICEV in a parasitic relationship. Even though the relationship between ICEV and BEV remained the same from the first to the second episode, the value that was estimated for the external interaction parameters changed. As a matter of fact, the extent to which BEV benefited from the parasitic relationship with ICEV in the first episode turned out to be entirely different from the extent to which BEV benefited from the parasitic relationship with ICEV in the second episode. Evidences from other studies also confirm such shifting in modes of interaction. For instance, a shift from symbiosis or

commensalism to parasitism between the powertrain technologies in terms of technological knowledge development and collaborations [4, 5]. The temporal shiftings occur due to the changes or shifts of systems' behaviour which can be related to changing of endogenous (e.g. change of the technologies' attractiveness or carrying capacities) and exogenous factors (e.g. financial crisis or fuel price fluctuations) [4, 5, 15, 17, 47, 48].

Our results present significant managerial implications. The managers and policy makers in transportation and energy sectors may lower the risk of isolated innovation policy mixes by taking a fine-grained level of analysis of interrelated powertrain technologies and their wider context [4, 5, 49-52]. Innovation policy mixes not only may create positive or negative internal feedback in a powertrain technology, but they also might bring about positive or negative externalities (or mirror effects) in other powertrain technologies [4, 5]. This makes the policy mixes more of the nature of 'creative destruction', aiming for 'creation' of an emerging technology and 'destabilization' of the old [2, 50, 52, 53]. On the one hand, the policy mixes may reinforce the creation of newer but less promising powertrain technologies such as fuel cell vehicles (FCVs), and on the other hand, they may lead to the destabilization of a more mature powertrain technology with more promising attributes such as BEVs [2]. This in fact occurred when the California Air Resource Board (CARB), in response to the automakers' lawsuit in 2002, had to create an alternative compliance path that could provide options with greater flexibilities for the industry [4, 5]. As a result, FCV was included in the ZEV mandate with a large federal fund (2.3 billion dollars) and huge hype for development, while leaving BEV with production cease and disappointment.

Acknowledgments

No grant from any funding agencies has been received for this research.

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Authors

Amir Mirzadeh Phirouzabadi is currently a PhD candidate in International Business at The University of Newcastle, Australia. He obtained his MSc. in Innovation and Technology Management in 2012 at Amirkabir University of Technology, Tehran, Iran. His main research interest is in socio-technical systems, sustainable transitions, industry dynamics, innovation networks, and science, technology & innovation policies, where he has authored and co-authored books, book chapters, conference papers and refereed journal articles such as *Journal of Cleaner Production*, *Transport Policy*, and *Data in Brief*. The aim in his PhD is to conceptualise and model the socio-technical interactions between technologies, and in particular powertrain technologies. He explores and simulates the complex behaviour as well as the dynamics and co-dynamics of technologies using System Dynamics modelling (via VENSIM), with a long horizon of over 50 years.

Dr. David Savage's research focuses on behavioural decision-making in extreme conditions and environments, such as the analysis of disasters (natural and man-made), high stress work or play environments (mountain climbers, elite athletes to police officers) and end-of-life decisions (euthanasia or suicide). behavioural economics. While this interest stems from a behavioural economics viewpoint, it extends into the broader social sciences by reintroducing the behavioural aspects of the social sciences with the empirical rigour of economics. In doing so creating a multi-disciplinary viewpoint, with a clearer understanding of theory and stronger empirical basis for the study of the decisions making and stronger methodological approach.

Dr. Karen Blackmore is a Senior Lecturer in Information Technology at the University of Newcastle. She is a spatial scientist with expertise in the modelling and simulation of complex social and environmental systems. Her research interests cover the use of agent-based models for simulation of socio-spatial interactions, and the use of simulation, virtual environments, and games for serious purposes. Her research is cross-disciplinary and empirical in nature, and extends to exploration of the ways that humans engage and interact with models and simulations. She has expertise in the study of affective processing, data mining and analytics, experimental design and physiological measurement, with research considering how best to quantify the complex interactions occurring in digital environments.

Dr. James Juniper is a lecturer in Economics with the Newcastle School of Business. Before entering academic life in 1990, James has worked as a policy practitioner and researcher in both the Commonwealth and State Public Services. He was also seconded to the United Trades and Labor Council in South Australia for a twelve-month period in 1986-1987, where he worked with both "blue-collar" and public sector unions. His research interests include Post-Keynesian Macroeconomics, Continental Philosophy, Environmental and Economic Modelling, Social Aspects of Computing, and Innovation Policy. In 2018 he published a Routledge Research Monograph on "The Economic Philosophy of the Internet of Things". He is an advocate of Modern Monetary Theory and an Associate of the Centre for Full Employment and Equity (CofFEE) at the University of Newcastle.